

Communication plan: Communication and engagement strategy

WP6: COMMUNICATING AND EXCHANGING KNOWLEDGE AND ENGAGEMENT
TASK 6.1: ELABORATE THE RESTPOLL OVERALL COMMUNICATION,
ENGAGEMENT AND IMPACT STRATEGY

Deliverable 6.1 & 6.4

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Version 2

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RestPoll

**Restoring Pollinator habitats across European agricultural
landscapes based on multi-actor participatory approaches**

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	5
2. Goal.....	5
3. Target audience and actor analysis	5
Target audience.....	5
Actor analysis	6
Relevant projects and partners	7
4. Positioning and message	7
Positioning of RestPoll in the “market”.....	7
Core message for external communication	7
5. Communication strategy.....	8
Approach.....	8
Internal communication.....	8
Corporate communication.....	8
Project communication.....	10
6. Creative concept.....	10
Project branding	10
Logo.....	10
Templates.....	11
Practical requirements.....	11
7. Means of communication	11
The faces behind RestPoll	12
Did you know that.....	12
Field work.....	13
In practice	13
8. Planning	15
9. Responsibilities.....	15
10. Appendixes (templates and concepts).....	17
10.1 Division of Roles and Responsibilities	17
Process content.....	17
Roles and responsibilities.....	17
10.2 Monitoring and evaluation.....	18
10.3 Brand guide	19
10.4 Template columns.....	19

Template – The faces behind RestPoll.....	19
Template – Did you know that.....	19
Template – Field work.....	19
Template – In practice	19
10.5 Template newsletter.....	20
10.6 Template social media.....	21
10.7 Outreach (social media) plan.....	23
Strategy newsletter RestPoll	23
Number of newsletter subscribers.....	23
Contents.....	23
Website.....	24
Promotion.....	24
Involvement.....	24
Researching the interest of the target group – for December 2024.....	24
Subject line	24
A/B Testing – for December 2024.....	24
Strategy social media	25
Following.....	25
Engagement.....	25
Promotion.....	25
Content.....	25

1. Introduction

RestPoll is a pan-European project dedicated to reversing the decline of wild pollinators and promoting sustainable pollination services across agricultural landscapes in Europe. The project's success depends on robust communication, engagement, and knowledge exchange efforts to reach various stakeholders and audiences effectively.

This communication and engagement strategy for RestPoll outlines and discusses the objectives, tactics, tools and metrics regarding communication of the project in all stages ranging from dissemination to evaluation, along with our engagement strategy with stakeholders involved in the project.

Version 2 includes an additional section, 10.7 Outreach (social media) plan, which highlights the plan for further outreach within the project and our strategy to increase subscribers and reach.

2. Goal

The goal of the RestPoll communication and engagement strategy is to reach a wide range of stakeholders and audiences interested in and relevant to the project's goals and objectives. It aims to engage and inform these audiences, fostering support and participation in the RestPoll project. The goals encompass:

1. To raise awareness about the RestPoll project and the significance of the decline in wild pollinators and their habitats.
2. To engage stakeholders at various levels (including farmers, researchers, policymakers, and the general public) and scales in the restoration efforts.
3. To communicate project findings, tools and recommendations to a broad audience.
4. To promote collaboration and knowledge exchange among project partners.

3. Target audience and actor analysis

Target audience

The primary target audiences for the RestPoll communication plan include:

1. Agricultural stakeholders:
 - Farmers, agricultural organizations and communities, landowners, and businesses involved in agriculture and land management, as they play a critical role in implementing pollinator-friendly practices.
 - Size: ~3500 farms (includes farms participating within RestPoll, plus additional entities)
2. Scientific community and educational institutions:
 - Scientific community: researchers, scientists, and academics in the fields of biology, ecology, environmental, social sciences, and related disciplines who can benefit from and contribute to the project's research findings and knowledge dissemination.
 - Size: ~50 institutes (including institutes involved in RestPoll)

- Educational institutions: schools, universities, and educational programmes interested in integrating pollinator conservation and restoration into their curricula and research projects.
 - Size: ~30 institutions (around 2 institutions per partner country)
- 3. Politicians
 - Local politicians within the case study areas, along with EU level politicians that are involved in agricultural measures and policies. Global political entities?
 - Size: ~18 local authorities, ~5 EU level authorities
- 4. The general public interested in biodiversity and environmental issues:
 - General Public: members of the public who have an interest in environmental conservation, biodiversity, pollinators, and sustainable agriculture, as they can be engaged to raise awareness and support the project's objectives.
 - Local communities and civil society.
 - Size: ~2,000 (attendance through demonstrations and workshops, participation online through social media)
- 5. Environmental and conservation NGO's:
 - Non-governmental organizations focused on environmental conservation, biodiversity, and sustainable land use, as they can provide support and advocacy for the project's goals.
 - Size: ~20 additional institutions

Actor analysis

An analysis of the many different actors for RestPoll is displayed in the table below. It provides a structured inventory of the involved parties. Actors of RestPoll consist of groups active on local, national, European and global levels. As the actors in these groups each have their own interests and goals, they each have different roles within the project. This varies from using the output of the project for scientific knowledge, in practice, for governance, to exert influence and to be used by the general public. The stakeholders have been plotted in the table below accordingly to this information.

	Local	National	European	Global
(scientific) knowledge		Universities, private sector	Horizon consortia (SG, Spring, PB, SC), IUCN	IPBES
Users in practice	Farmers, landowners, site managers, contractors, beekeepers	Implementing organisations, food chain (primary production, processing, retail)		UNDP, BESNET
Users governance	local and regional politicians, policy makers	national politicians, ministries, policy makers, research	EU Parliament, EU	CBD, FAO

		institutes (Inrae, RIVM, PBL, INBO, etc.), NGO	Commission, DGN-ENV, DG-agri JRC, IEEP, COR	
Users influencers	Local stakeholders	NGOs, Agricultural and horticultural organisations, landowners, national business and biodiversity platforms	COPA-COGECA, ELO, WWF, European B@B Platform	Apimondia, The Capitals Coalition, We Value Nature Initiative
Users public	consumers, local residents	Consumers' Association, Educational Institutions		

Relevant projects and partners

Relevant projects and partners include previous projects such as PoshBee, Nutrib2, and SUPER-B, on-going projects, such as SHOWCASE, Promote Pollinators, or Safeguard, or future/newly funded projects, such as ARION or WildPosh. These established projects and partners can be approached to share content from RestPoll. This shall be further elaborated on in chapter 5.

4. Positioning and message

Positioning of RestPoll in the “market”

RestPoll aims at contributing to the conservation of biodiversity and sustainable agriculture in Europe. The project positions Europe as a global leader in pollinator restoration. RestPoll will be uniquely positioned as an influential partner in EU and global biodiversity restoration, by disseminating research and enabling target groups to implement the results in their daily work.

Core message for external communication

The goal of RestPoll is to permanently restore and connect pollinator habitats in Europe. It aims to provide society with tools to reverse wild pollinator declines and to position Europe as a global leader in pollinator restoration. To counteract the decline of pollinators and thus pollination services, it is important to restore their flowering and nesting habitats. RestPoll will, together with stakeholders ranging from individual land managers to governments, focus on measures and cross-sectoral approaches to restore pollinators and their services. Central to RestPoll is the establishment of a Europe-wide network of pollinator restoration case-study areas and Living Labs (LL), which are unique hubs for experimentation, demonstration, and mutual learning.

The RestPoll consortium combines expertise from sixteen countries ranging from natural and social scientists, twenty-four research institutions, one NGO, three

businesses, two ministries and one national park. Stakeholders along the food value chain will be engaged through newly developed participatory approaches at diverse social, ecological, and political scales.

5. Communication strategy

Approach

The RestPoll project is committed to transparent and effective communication, both internally among consortium members and externally with stakeholders, researchers, policymakers, and the wider public. Our communication strategy is based on doing it together. Committed (communication) professionals of different organisations join forces to jointly achieve (communicative) success. Making maximum impact with limited means and funds is crucial. In practice this also means that the project utilizes channels of others. This is elaborated on in the paragraph about corporate communication below. The outlined communication methods and channels are designed to ensure that its impact is far-reaching and meaningful. This concise plan conveys clear, understandable, coordinated and effective messages, thus, raising awareness and maximising the benefits resulting from the RestPoll project.

By putting the wishes and needs of the target group first at important decision moments, creative communication solutions are delivered that are sustainably successful. By considering the perspective of the target audience at an early stage, we set the tone for an externally focused communication approach in which our starting point is the problem as recognised in the “real world”. Communication activities contribute, on the one hand, to positioning RestPoll in the environment of practitioners and policymakers at regional, national, EU and global levels. On the other hand, communication activities will focus on sharing research results and enabling target groups to implement the results in their daily work.

In order to reach the best results for the communication strategy everyone must work together, and a three-pronged approach must be used. This approach consists of internal communication, corporate communication and project communication.

Internal communication

Many people from various parts of Europe work on the project. Furthermore, many different systems are used within RestPoll. As not all project partners are tech savvy, it is necessary to keep things simple where possible. Everyone contributes from their own role and responsibility. In collaboration with the experts from the different WPs, we will create relevant and accessible content. The danger is that everyone works on their own part, but there is no sense of cohesion/belonging to the project. There it is important that everyone gets updated actively and feels part of the project. To have maximum impact with a limited budget, we will use the channels (websites, newsletters, social media channels, etc.) of the participating professionals and their organisations, and other relevant platforms to provide relevant content on channels and media that our target groups rely on and are familiar with.

Corporate communication

The project calls for a campaign like approach in which you think about how to position yourself with regards to others, particularly with limited means and funds, whilst

making maximum impact. Furthermore, the results, milestones and education materials need to be shared. That means the available resources must be used wisely in terms of getting input from people and utilizing funds. Therefore, RestPoll uses mainly reoccurring columns to share its content. This ensures that readers see recognizable formats, whilst it ensures that HVR Group and project coordinators can utilize the resources as optimally as possible. It highlights various topics from quarterly updates on the project to sharing information about Living Labs. All topics are categorized and grouped together based on the subject. The columns are recognizable due to the icons each category of column has. This content is shared on the social media channels, referred to as news items on the website and in the newsletter. In line with the project communication being recognizable, the columns have a catchy title and a recognizable template for social media stories and posts. More information on the columns can be found in chapter 6 and the templates for input on these columns can be found in chapter 10.

Risk management

There are several risks which have been assessed at the start of the project. Mitigating these risks ensures that the project is as successful as possible. Risks include project partners not feeling as though they are part of RestPoll. Therefore, they might not optimally share their progress within the project. The risk is that project partners don't optimally benefit from each other's work. It is also to the detriment of positioning RestPoll, as people are less inclined to do so if they don't feel part of the project. These risks can be mitigated by sending out frequent internal updates regarding the project. It will be a short update and includes what the person involved in thinks is the most fun or interesting thing. Another way this can be mitigated is by actively involving people in gathering content to be shared and putting those involved in the spotlight. This is done by proactively getting frequent and relevant input from work package leaders. This will be mitigated by the easy-to-use templates, as mentioned above.

Furthermore, the limited resources the project has means that channels of stakeholders must be utilized to get maximum impact. The risk is that the stakeholders are not people who will follow the corporate channels and therefore dissemination is also dependent on channels of others. Therefore, to mitigate this risk and utilize the budget as efficient as possible it is essential that relevant high-quality content is created and disseminated amongst appropriate channels. Subsequently relying on other channels to spread the content is in itself also a risk. Therefore, clear instructions must be given and good relationships with stakeholders are important. This can be done by making good use of the existing connections, e.g. making use of the contacts and positions which Work Package leaders and members have. In addition, the connections which project members have will be inventoried by means of a survey. This can lead to contacts willing to share news regarding RestPoll.

Educational material which is deemed inappropriate for the cultures in which it will be disseminated is a risk. Therefore, material which is deemed acceptable for all cultures must be created. This can be done by working together with those who can assess what is appropriate. Language can be a risk when specifically focusing on educational materials as these are meant to educate young people, many of whom are not proficient

enough yet in the English language. This can be mitigated by assessing the required languages amongst the target audiences and creating educational material in these languages.

Project communication

In order to facilitate project communication and to help with these challenges, materials have been created in the form of a toolbox containing means of corporate communication. It consists of materials such as a PowerPoint template, core message, fact sheet, animations and images. All these materials can be found in the member area of the RestPoll website and are mentioned in more detail in chapter 6. In the future materials such as educational material and posters will be created.

6. Creative concept

Project branding

All content for RestPoll must be in line with the project's visual identity and overall corporate appearance created for the project. As a foundation of the future effective communication activities, a sound set of working dissemination tools and materials was crucial to be established within the first months of the project. The brand guide, project logo, project promotional materials and a public website (www.RestPoll.eu) were created to form the main tools of project public visibility.

[The brand guide](#) to the RestPoll visual identity contains all essential guidelines created for all project partners. This has been made available on the project website. The guide is meant to serve as a reference point for all project partners, aiming to guarantee a consistent and continuous presentation of project outputs, such as promotional materials. It includes requirements for communication materials and various versions of the logo visual materials that aim to promote and strengthen the visual identity and corporate image of the project. Project branding consists of the logo and branding such as a PowerPoint template and brand guide. All items are available and easy to access for all partners upon accessing the member area of the project's website (via login). The project website is developed as the main dissemination channel.

Logo

The logo for RestPoll has been developed in close collaboration with the RestPoll coordinator and project manager. It was designed to help the external audience to easily identify RestPoll and it contributes to the project visibility by providing a corporate identity from the very beginning of the project. Various versions of the logo have been created. [All versions of the logo](#) are available to the consortium to use in official communication.

Fig. 1 RestPoll logo (original version).

Templates

Various templates for the project were created contributing to the project visibility and in line with the corporate identity. For example, the PowerPoint template for RestPoll was created for all project partners to use a consistent visual presentation in PowerPoint on project-related topics. It is for both internal and external use. A set of corporate templates was also produced and uploaded to the member area of the RestPoll website to facilitate future dissemination and reporting activities such as milestones and deliverable reports.

In addition, templates for a newsletter and social media posts were created in line with the corporate identity. See appendixes 10.5 and 10.6. Available resources must be used wisely in terms of getting input from people and utilizing funds. To ensure that maximum impact can be made with limited means, RestPoll uses mainly reoccurring columns to share its content as previously mentioned. This ensures that readers see recognizable formats, whilst it ensures that HVR Group and project coordinators can utilize the resources as optimally as possible. This content is shared on the social media channels, referred to as news items on the website and in the newsletter. In line with the project communication being recognizable, all four columns each have their own icon and a recognizable template. To gather this input, a template for all interviewees of the columns is provided. This template is sent to the people who can provide information relevant to the project to be shared on the various communication channels. The four categories of columns are further elaborated on in chapter 7 and the templates can be found in chapter 10.

Practical requirements

All communication, dissemination and exploitation activities of the project must be in line with the brand guide, Gender equality and diversity plan (M 25), and the Communication and management plan (D7.1) of RestPoll.

7. Means of communication

Throughout the duration of the project, content will be disseminated. As previously mentioned, this shall be done via a mix of four types of external channels. These channels are complementary to each other and be utilised for different goals. The figure below discusses the main communication channels and what they will be used for.

These channels are all filled with content categorized by the previously mentioned columns. These columns highlight various topics ranging from quarterly updates on the project to sharing information about Living Labs. All topics are categorized and grouped together based on the subject. The columns are recognizable due to the icons each category of column has. This content is shared on the social media channels, referred to as news items on the website and in the newsletter. In line with the project communication being recognizable, the columns have a catchy title and a recognizable template for social media stories and posts. The templates for input on these columns can be found in chapter 10. The categories for the columns are elaborated on below.

The faces behind RestPoll

This column consists of introducing all partners, work package leaders and the project coordinator, Alexandra Klein. It is divided into two topics:

- **Introduce all 30 partners:** the kick-off took place at the end of 2023. Now the project and its website are officially up and running, all 30 partners of the project can be introduced by organisation. This can be done roughly biweekly during 2024. The text could also be used on the website of RestPoll. The introduction includes all team members, their motivation for joining the project and their role in it.
- **Work package leaders and RestPoll coordinator:** introducing all work package leaders and the RestPoll coordinator, Alexandra Klein. The introduction includes all team members, their motivation for joining the project and their role in it.

External channel	Use of channel
Project website	Sharing milestones and important updates, scientific papers, policy briefs, educational material, and project reports for sharing research findings with scientific community, policymakers and public.
Social media	Informing and engaging the target audience by sharing milestones and updates on the project. Plus provide educational information in line with the research conducted.
Newsletter	Sharing updates on the project and introducing the people involved.
Events	Showcase RestPoll's progress and engage with various audiences by organizing events for the general public, workshops and seminars and participating in events and conferences.

Did you know that...

This column consists of interesting updates, articles and (quarterly) updates on the project. It will also include reposting from other organisations and partners. It encompasses five topics:

- **General updates on project:** in addition, general updates on the project can be shared on social media. These can range from reaching milestones and deliverables to general updates.
- **Quarterly updates:** sharing quarterly results and explaining how they are applicable to other stakeholders. Graphics can be used if necessary.
- **Did you know that...:** interesting facts that can be shared about the project.
- **Relevant articles:** sharing articles which are of interest, including explanations.
- **Repost from other organisations and partners:** if a clear link can be made to RestPoll, posts from other organisations and partners such as PenSoft and PennState

can be reshared. This includes conferences, papers from similar project, or information which is deemed relevant.

Field work

This column is all about field work, case study areas and demonstration sites. It also includes highlighting pollinators and plants of interest. It encompasses five topics:

- **Field work:** field work will also be highlighted as and when this occurs. At least [eighteen partners](#) will be doing field work throughout Europe. Most field work will be known by project manager, Amibeth Thompson.
- **Pollinators/Plants:** pollinators are an important player in the project. We will highlight pollinator species or groups, including their importance as pollinators (i.e. specialized interactions with plants), recognizable characteristics, and facts to help bring a personal dimension to this group of insects and help inform the general public, and tips on how to help monitor or restore their habitats. In the same way, plants are also important for providing resources for pollinators and will also be highlighted.
- **Monitoring:** different methods of monitoring have been or will be implemented in the case study areas. We will highlight these different methods, explaining how they are implemented and what the results can tell us. We will use this platform to introduce or promote established or new methods/platforms, targeted especially towards citizen science.
- **Case study areas:** different case study areas will be introduced when possible, including information such the implemented restoration measures and their role within the project framework. We will most likely not be able to share spatially explicit information due to our privacy policy.
- **Demonstration sites:** an annual workshop will be held at our demonstration sites. This workshop, and the results which come from it, can be promoted.

In practice

This column will give more information about how various topics are put into practice and what their importance is. For example: living labs, what you can do and the measures that are taken. It encompasses four topics:

- **Living labs:** what are they, what is their importance, where (in the world) are they?
- **Nature protected/Farming systems/Measures:** describe the different types of farming systems and the measures that are implemented. Explain why they are important and what results we gain from or hope to gain from their implementation.
- **What can you do (monitoring):** provide resources and information about how to implement certain measures in your daily life. For example, explain how to create a bee hotel, create a pollinator friendly balcony, participate in citizen science monitoring programs, etc.
- **Current or future applications:** updates on current or future policy changes implemented to support pollinators, promote monitoring, or change land use management. Development of tools, programs, or projects to implement these or other changes.

The remaining duration of the project is 42 months. Own content will be shared on average twice a week, with reposting of relevant posts or events throughout. During the first stage of the project the focus is on content which introduces the project and the people working on it. As the project progresses the emphasis shifts to content which shares more about the results which have been reached. This is reflected in the planning. As mentioned, the content can be categorised into four columns. They will be published on the social media channels. Additionally, they are posted as news items on the website and shared in the quarterly newsletter. A content calendar will be created based on the columns to ensure the process of creating and sharing content goes smoothly.

Column	The faces behind RestPoll	Did you know that...	Field work	In practice
Goal	Introducing all partners Work package leaders and RestPoll coordinator	Providing general updates on project, including quarterly updates. Also sharing relevant articles and reposting from other organizations and partners	Provide a glimpse of what field work is like, while also educating about the plants, pollinators, methods or sites where the field work is conducted	Provide information or news about how our research is put into practice or the practical application it has in the governance and technological sector
Frequency	Biweekly from April 2024	Throughout the project in sync with the social posts, when the 7 quarterly updates occur, 24 deliverables are met and when it occurs (reposting). Maximum of 40 times.	Throughout the project when 18 case study areas are visited, twice annually to promote the workshop. Maximum of 30 times.	Throughout the project monthly or when relevant news or developments occur. Minimum of 40 times.

8. Planning

The project shall run until September 2027. Throughout the project content will be shared. This communication plan contains the strategy to communicate, engage and make an impact with communication. Its plans will be executed until September 2027. The strategy includes sharing content on various channels with help of the templates. The templates to gather information will be used from April 2024 by stakeholders. These templates and the process to gather information to disseminate with help of said templates will be assessed during April and May. If required, changes can be made in this process. As mentioned, content will be gathered and disseminated throughout the duration of the project via the newsletter, website and social media channels. The frequency discussed in chapter 7 will be utilized.

Furthermore, in June 2024 discussions will be started with the project coordinator regarding organizing network events. Additionally, discussion will also be held about developing specific tools and actions to enable social engagement with TUM. Lastly a report on CED activities will be started. These are all to be concluded before September 2027.

Although the official funding period for the project concludes in September 2027, the activities for the project shall continue until September 2029. Therefore, the website and social media channels will be maintained during this period. Materials such as policy recommendations, tool kits and educational materials shall still be additionally disseminated through other channels, such as the Horizon Dashboard and Horizon Results Platform. Papers published during this period will be made available as well as mentioning future or potential follow-up projects. In addition, a dissemination and exploitation plan will be shared in month 18 and revised in month 36 of the project.

9. Responsibilities

HVR Group shall stay in regular contact with the project manager, Amibeth Thompson, through weekly meetings to discuss the progress that has been made and upcoming issues. They shall also discuss content to be shared via social media, the project website and newsletter. All social media accounts have been created by the project manager.

HVR Group and the project coordinator and manager have a clear division regarding the tasks surrounding social media. This means HVR group is in charge of producing various reoccurring posts to use on the social media channels of RestPoll. These are approved by the RestPoll project coordinator, Alexandra Klein, and manager.

In practice, this means the project manager reaches out to people to get input for social media purposes. HVR Group receives their input or gets into contact with these people to create content for social media. HVR Group is in charge of content creation and social media management, including regular posting and engagement. If deemed relevant, stakeholders are approached to complete the templates as mentioned in chapter 10.4. Due to the relevancy of the topics, they must complete the templates within five

working days of having received it. Therefore, if follow-up questions need to be posed there is time to do so.

The specific process and division of responsibilities between the RestPoll project coordinator and HVR Group can be found in chapter 10.1.

10. Appendixes (templates and concepts)

10.1 Division of Roles and Responsibilities

Process content

The possible content will be discussed during their weekly meetings. This content will range from reoccurring posts to ad hoc posts. Once an agreement has been reached, HVR Group will discuss this with a content manager from their organisation and ask them to contact the people needed to gather the input for content in question. The templates will be accessible to HVR Group (communication advisor and content manager) as well as the RestPoll project coordinator. The content manager at HVR Group ensures the content on social media, the website and in the newsletter is sent out. The passwords to all social media accounts and the project website are stored on OnePassword. They can be accessed by HVR Group and the RestPoll project coordinator.

Roles and responsibilities

RestPoll Project Coordinator and Manager:

1. **Content Collection:** Gather project updates, research findings, and news from internal sources.
2. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Engage with stakeholders, answer inquiries, and foster relationships.
3. **Event Promotion:** Promote project-related events, webinars, and workshops.
4. **Networking:** Connect with other relevant organizations and researchers in the field.
5. **Data Sharing:** Share project-related data and open-access resources on social media.

HVR Group:

1. **Content Creation:** Develop visually appealing content such as infographics, videos, and articles.
2. **Content Scheduling:** Schedule and post content on social media platforms.
3. **Hashtag Strategy:** Develop and use project-specific hashtags for consistent branding.
4. **Response Management:** Monitor comments and messages, respond to inquiries, and moderate discussions.
5. **Analytics and Reporting:** Provide regular reports on social media performance and suggest improvements.

Shared Responsibilities:

1. **Social Media Calendar:** Collaborate on creating a monthly content calendar.
2. **Review and Approval:** Ensure all content aligns with project objectives and messaging.

3. **Crisis Management:** Prepare for and respond to any social media crises or negative feedback.

10.2 Monitoring and evaluation

The effects of our work are measured by evaluating the actual results (output), determining what dissemination may contribute to our objectives (outcomes) and developing our communication strategy and activities to maximize this input.

The table below gives an overview of how RestPoll measures and verifies impact. The Integrated Evaluation Framework for planning and setting SMART objectives, defining success, and the measurement and evaluation itself. Every year, the achieved results are record in a 3-page summary (as part of a communication report) reflecting on the opportunities for improving communication activities. In addition regular evaluations of communication materials will be held between HVR Group and the project coordinator.

Table: Summary of measures to maximise impact and total target values for indicators verifying success

Tool	Target group(s)	Contribution of impact	Verification of use with target indicator values
Main forms of communication and knowledge exchange			
Website	Project-relevant stakeholders, researchers, and society at large	Main communication and knowledge exchange interface to engage	#visits (>10,000), time spent (>mean 2min), #pages visited (>average of 2/visit), downloads (>600), access by stakeholders (>100)
e-learning	Farmers, gardeners, other land managers, agricultural schools, beekeepers, business actors, farm advisors, public administration bodies	Easy access to methods and approaches developed in WP6 with the participation of all partners	#visits (>1.000), time spent (>mean 4min), downloads (>300), social media activity (shared in >50 channels), #European countries (>20)
Open archive	Project-relevant stakeholders, researchers, public administration bodies	Open access to papers, reports, and other deliverables	#visits (>300), time spent (>mean 4min), downloads (>200)
Social media	Society at large incl. journalists, politicians etc.	Ongoing announcements of activities & outcomes	#posts (>1,000), #retweets (>500)
Social engagement			
Tools (e.g. educational videos, flipbooks, policy briefs, labelling)	Farmers, gardeners, other land managers, agricultural schools, beekeepers, business actors, farm advisors, Indigenous people, public administration bodies	Promotion of the project, enable social engagement	Brand awareness & adaptable logo (1), #visits of all tools (>4,000), reach (>14 countries), downloads (>200)
Network events and Living Labs	Stakeholders	Building relationships, facilitate interaction & knowledge exchange e.g. farmer-to-policy maker	#attendees (>600), interacting (>100), contributions (>200), mean rating (>7.5 out of 10), #countries (>10)
Public events	Public at large, Human health specialists, local	Sharing outcomes	#attendees (>1,000), reach

	communities, Indigenous people		(>10 countries), mean rating (>7,5 out of 10), #countries (>10)
Press release	Journalists, general public, policy	Announcement of outcomes, raising public awareness & necessity of policy adaptations	List of publications & broadcasts with broad coverage (>20)
Support and teaching material			
RestPoll toolbox and inventories	All relevant stakeholders	Support key stakeholders to take appropriate action themselves	Downloads (>500), reach (stakeholders of all partner countries & 5 countries outside Europe)
Teaching material	Farmers, gardeners, other land managers, other land users, agricultural schools, beekeepers, business actors, farm advisors, public administration bodies	Sharing research outcomes, enabling target groups to implement the results in their daily work	Downloads (300), reach (>14 countries), social media activity (75 channels, >250 posts)
Support events and training	Professionals	Harmonising data & increasing research quality	List of supported events (2), #attendees (>25)

10.3 Brand guide

[The brand guide](#) can be found on the RestPoll website.

10.4 Template columns

The following templates are to be published on the social media pages and website of RestPoll. The recognizable icons per column can be found in the RestPoll brand guide.

Template – The faces behind RestPoll

The template for [this column](#) can be found in Microsoft Forms.

Template – Did you know that...

The template for [this column](#) can be found in Microsoft Forms.

Template – Field work

The template for [this column](#) can be found in Microsoft Forms.

Template – In practice

The template for [this column](#) can be found in Microsoft Forms.

10.5 Template newsletter

[Beleik de wistversie](#)

Dear [Name],

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Suspendisse ac malesuada ex. Proin rutrum faucibus est non ultrices. Aliquam erat volutpat. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Suspendisse ac malesuada ex. Proin rutrum faucibus est non ultrices. Aliquam erat volutpat.

Title news item

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Suspendisse ac malesuada ex. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.

[Read more](#)

Title news item

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Suspendisse ac malesuada ex.

[Read more](#)

Title news item

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Suspendisse ac malesuada ex.

[Read more](#)

Title news item

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Suspendisse ac malesuada ex.

[Read more](#)

RestPOL
University of Freiburg
Chair of Nature Conservation and Landscape Ecology
Tennishofstrasse 4
79106 Freiburg
Germany

SPREAD THE NEWS

Unsubscribe

If you no longer wish to receive the newsletter, you can unsubscribe.

Dit e-mail bericht is verzonden aan [\(email\)](#).
Als u geen nieuwsbrief meer wilt ontvangen, kunt u zich [hier afmelden](#).
U kunt ook uw gegevens [inzien en wijzigen](#).
Voor een goede ontvangst voegt u [\(from_email\)](#) toe aan uw adresboek.

10.6 Template social media

Figure 1 Social posts columns

Figure 2 Social post carousel

 The faces behind RestPoll

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat.

[→](#)

 Field work

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat.

[Read more](#)
^

Figure 3 Social posts stories

10.7 Outreach (social media) plan

This appendix is to fulfil Deliverable 6.4 "Communication Plan," which is a report on the external communication activities (outreach). As we have detailed our strategy for communication outreach in our D6.1 "Communication and engagement strategy," we have added this appendix to provide further details into the current plan for outreach within the project and our strategy to increase subscribers and reach. For the beginning phase of RestPoll, outreach mainly consists of the external newsletter and social media. Both share content in the recognizable four types of columns as mentioned above. As part of Milestone 23, the social media channels have been set-up and are regularly maintained. The first newsletter was sent out on 4 June 2024 and will be sent to all subscribers quarterly throughout the project. In September 2024 the newsletter had 112 subscribers. The social media channels respectively each had:

- [Instagram](#):
 - 97 followers
- [Facebook](#):
 - Likes: 32
 - Followers: 106
- [LinkedIn](#):
 - 217 followers

Now the newsletter and social media channels are up and running we want to increase the amount of people that are reached with them. Therefore, we have created a plan to expand our subscriber breadth for the newsletter and social media. This plan consists of easier to implement improvements and ideas and suggestions which require a bit more time. Therefore, we will start with simpler implementations and test solutions. Some plans can hopefully be implemented by September 2024, when the next newsletter will be sent out. Other suggestions will be implemented for subsequent newsletters, such as in December 2024.

Strategy newsletter RestPoll

The plan is to ensure that the number of people who subscribe to the newsletter is increased. In addition, a goal is also to have the articles be better read within the newsletter. The plans are outlined below.

Number of newsletter subscribers

We will increase the number of subscribers by paying attention to the content, adding options to sign-up for the newsletter on the website and increasing promotion through other channels.

Contents

- Topics: relevant, of value to readers and interesting to the target audience
 - Which topics and/or columns are popular? This will be investigated in the near future by means of newsletter analyses.
- Exclusive: the newsletter offers information that subscribers can't get anywhere else, e.g. early access to information such as invitations to events and other announcements.

- Invitations or announcements such as the date of next Annual Group Meeting sharing in the upcoming newsletters?
- Other exclusive information could include the pre-release of reports, documents,, promotional materials etc.

Website

- More sign-up forms have been added on the site, such as on:
 - News-page: <https://restpoll.eu/news/>
 - Member area: there is now an option to sign up for both the internal and external newsletter
- Optimize Call to action (CTA)
 - Text: we can entice website visitors with exclusivity by emphasizing in the CTA that the newsletters contain exclusive information
 - Design: use pop-ups, slide-ins, and sticky bars to make the CTA stand out

In the future, the website might be available in various languages. This helps cater to the international stakeholders.

Promotion

- Promote newsletter via social media channels
- Ask partners to promote the newsletters
- Promote signing up and visiting the website through outreach materials such as flyers, posters, or presentations
- Add a sign-up link to personal email signatures from Amibeth, for example
- For the newsletter in December 2024: investigate which sources generate the most sign-ups and promote accordingly

Involvement

We can ensure that articles are better visited by researching the interest of the target group.

Researching the interest of the target group – for December 2024

- Newsletter analytics: based on the analytics, we can assess which categories and topics are popular.
- Input from readers: we can proactively ask readers what they would like to receive information about, for example by means of a poll.
- Reader feedback: send out a survey to ask what readers like and what they want to see more of.

Subject line

- Short, engaging, and relevant to arouse curiosity and invite the reader to open.
- Personalization: We can put the recipient's name in the subject line.

A/B Testing – for December 2024

We can perform A/B tests to analyse the effects and if necessary. A/B testing is a way to experiment with two or more variants of the same newsletter, to figure out which performs better. For example, at random set of subscribers is sent a version of the newsletter with a particular title and another group receives a version of the newsletter with a different title. A/B tests can also be conducted with variants such as layout,

images, length of text for example. Based on the findings from the A/B tests, the newsletter can be improved accordingly.

Strategy social media

Following

We can increase the number of followers and engagement by paying attention to the content, improving the engagement with other accounts and promoting the socials through other channels.

Engagement

- 3x a week 10 min online engagement (starting with Instagram).
- Create a simple reel (just animated or minimal video content/editing) twice a month. Videos of spotted bees or videos showcasing an article with some gifs/animation.

Promotion

- Promote social media channels by sending emails to partners (in the project) introducing our social media channels and activating them to follow. This mail includes a share package/social kit created for partners and other people related to RP with i.e.:
 - A social post for their own channels
 - Tips and tricks to help the RP socials grow
- Send emails to other (non-related but relevant) organisations and/or create a press list to send updates to while actively attracting them to our social media.
- Add social media buttons to personal email signatures from project members such as Alexandra, Nina and Amibeth.
- Organise a giveaway among the social media followers, encouraging them to share and follow. Make this giveaway known among the partners and in the newsletter.
 - Create a big giveaway and advertise this.
- Create physical posters and flyers activating people to follow the socials (and newsletter). Send these out to partnering institutes and university's so they can hang the posters in their hallways.
 - Buy advertorial space in university magazines/relevant media to advertise our channels.

Content

Furthermore, during the Annual Group Meeting in Freiburg input for relevant and interesting content will be collected in the form of photos of interesting attendees and articles written about the Annual Group Meeting. In addition, attendees will be asked to share their ideas for potential content to share on the social media channels. The precise details will be announced in the coming weeks.